

game studies after capital-a "Art"

Gaming exists stuck between regimes.

On one side, traditional cultural institutions and bourgeois artistic discourses continue to exert gravity - striving to assimilate games into known terrain by elevating select works as aesthetic accomplishments, fetishizing formalist "purity," and reifying myths of individual creative genius. In its yearning for legitimacy, game studies has often contorted itself to cater to these established notions of what constitutes culturally significant "Art."

On the other side, gaming's unstable material realities continuously undermine such idealist abstractions. Games are embedded within techno-capitalist systems of valorization, commodification, and labor extraction. They function as innovative vectors for monetizing captured attention and policing normative modes of participatory "play." Gaming's community ecosystems continuously mutate between official/unofficial spheres, centralized control and autonomous disruptions, normative practices and emergent resistance.

Caught within gaming's paradoxical rift, its anarchic virtualities actively corrode rigid boundaries between production/consumption, high/low cultural capital, institutional validation/marginalization and systemic inclusion/subversive abjection.

First, this paper analytically maps how conventional art world criteria and institutional regimes of legitimation systematically fail to adequately grasp gaming's complexities. Case studies highlight the profound disconnect between how gaming phenomena get codified through elite cultural lenses versus their lateral circulations and alternative processes of meaning-making.

Secondly, the analysis turns to theorizing gaming's paradoxical roles as both ubiquitous entertainment commodities locked in capitalist valorization cycles and catalyzing fronts where techno-cultural participation and social fabrication fundamentally reshape regimes of cultural production, technological mediation, and the very concept of aesthetic "works."

Third, the focus shifts to game studies' relationship to fields of power and struggle over cultural capital. Game studies have historically pursued legitimacy by aligning with bourgeois fields that arbitrate what qualifies as rarefied capital-A "Art." This risks subjugating gaming's unruly materialities to ideological capture and representation as stable aesthetic objects validated by elite cultural spheres.

Finally, the presentation does not aim to resolve these tensions into a new totalizing theory of "what games are." Rather, it argues game studies must relinquish their compulsions towards ontological stability and intelligibility dictated by established regimes of cultural value. They need flexible conceptual frameworks attuned to gaming's radical contingencies - frameworks prioritizing indeterminacy and generative frictions capable of productively contaminating all received epistemological, representational, and bodily disciplines.

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